

Rhazya Alkaloids

(MRS.) A. CHATTERJEE, J. BANERJI and A. BANERJI

Pure Chemistry Department, Calcutta University, Calcutta 700009

SINCE the discovery of quinine and morphine in the earlier part of the last century, alkaloids have played an increasingly important role in natural product chemistry. Many of these compounds exhibit important physiological and pharmacodynamic properties, and have been widely used as drugs. The results of systematic chemical investigations of different botanical species have shown that plants of the *Apocynaceae* produce a large number of monomeric and dimeric indole alkaloids. These indole-derived compounds hold an important position among the alkaloids, by virtue of their wide structural variations, the fascinating variety of reactions they undergo and their widespread occurrence in nature.

A systematic survey has revealed that the following genera of *Apocynaceae* are rich sources of indole alkaloids: *Alstonia*, *Aspidosperma*, *Ervatamia*, *Geissospermum*, *Hunteria*, *Kopsia*, *Picalima*, *Rauwolfia*, *Rhazya*, *Tabernanthe*, *Vinca* and *Voacanga*. In the present article the chemistry of the alkaloids

obtained from the genus *Rhazya* (tribe: *Plumerieae*; subtribe: *Euplumerieae*) is described.

The genus *Rhazya* comprises only two species, viz. *R. stricta* Decaisne and *R. orientalis* A. DC. *R. stricta* is a small, glabrous, erect shrub growing profusely in the northwestern regions of the Indian sub-continent. The plant is reputed in folk medicine as a bitter tonic for sore throat, fever and general debility and also as a curative for chronic rheumatism¹⁻⁴. A systematic chemical investigation of this plant was first undertaken by the senior author of this review in the early 1940s⁵. Subsequent studies in the laboratory of the same investigator resulted in the isolation of a number of indole alkaloids of diverse structural types. The presence of some indole alkaloids have been reported from other laboratories. The shrub *R. orientalis* is indigenous to Greece and Turkey. A number of alkaloids have also been isolated from this plant. A list of all the alkaloids obtained from these two plants is given in Table I.

TABLE I—ALKALOIDS OBTAINED FROM THE TWO RHAZYA SPECIES

Sl. No.	Name of the Alkaloid Molecular Formula m. p. [α] _D (Solvent)	Structure	Source	References
1	2	3	4	5
<i>Strictosidine type</i>				
1.	Strictosidine (Isovincoside) $C_{27}H_{34}N_2O_9$ — —		<i>Rhazya stricta</i> (R.s.) <i>Rhazya orientalis</i> (R.o.)	6, 7
2.	5 α -Carboxystrictosidine $C_{23}H_{30}N_2O_{11}$ 232° -280° (MeOH)	5 α -Carboxystrictosidine	R.o.	8

1	2	3	4	5
3.	Demethylstrictosidine $C_{26}H_{32}N_2O_9$ — —	$-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ instead of $-\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$ at C_{16}	<i>R.o.</i>	8
4.	5 α -Carboxy-demethylstrictosidine $C_{27}H_{32}N_2O_{11}$ — —	$-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ instead of $-\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$ at C_{16} ; 5 α - CO_2H	<i>R.o.</i>	8
<i>Corynantheine type</i>				
5.	Geissoschizine (Alkaloid R1) $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$ 187° +72° (CHCl_3)		<i>R.s.</i>	9,10,11
<i>Hunterburnine type</i>				
6.	Rhazinine (Antirrhine) $C_{19}H_{24}N_2O$ 118° +4° (CHCl_3)		<i>R.s.</i>	9,10,11,12 13,17
7.	Vallesiachotamine $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_3$ 253-55° +160° (CHCl_3)		<i>R.o.</i>	14
<i>Sarpagine type</i>				
8.	Rhazine (Akuammidine) $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$ 234-36° +21° (EtOH)		<i>R.s.</i>	15,16,17,18
<i>Picaline type</i>				
9.	Strictamine (Vincamidine) $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O_2$ 110-12° +103°		<i>R.s.</i>	12,19
10.	Rhazinaline $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_3$ 137° +61° (EtOH)	16-Formyl—16-epistri- ctamine	<i>R.s.</i>	9,10,11,20
11.	16-Formylstrictamine $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_3$ — —	16-Formylstrictamine	<i>R.s.</i>	20

1	2	3	4	5
12.	Pictinine C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃ 223-25° —47° (CHCl ₃)		<i>R.o.</i>	14
13.	Picalinal C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ 179-180° —180° (CHCl ₃)	16-Formylpictinine	<i>R.o.</i>	14
<i>Aspidosperma alkaloids</i>				
14.	(—)-Quebrachamine C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ 147° —110° (CHCl ₃)		<i>R.s.</i>	17,18,21
15.	Rhazidine base (Rhazidigenine) C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O 183-85° —37° (EtOH)		<i>R.s.</i>	12,17,22,23,24
16.	(+)-Aspidospermidine C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ 120-21° +24° (EtOH)		<i>R.s.</i>	21,25
17.	(+)-1, 2-Dehydroaspidospermidine C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂ Amorph +227° (CHCl ₃)	(+) 1, 2-Dehydroaspidospermidine	<i>R.s.</i>	12,21,25
18.	(+)-Vincadifformine C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Amorph. +540° (EtOH) (±)-Vincadifformine C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ 124-25° 0°		<i>R.s.</i>	25
19.	Tabersonine C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ — —366° (EtOH)	6, 7-Dehydrovincadifformine	<i>R.o.</i>	26
<i>Eburnamine type</i>				
20.	Eburnamine C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂ O 181° —93° (CHCl ₃)	 EBURNAMINE TYPE 14-α-OH	<i>R.s.</i>	21

1	2	3	4	5
21.	Eburnamenine C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ Amorph. +183° (CHCl ₃)	14, 15 -Dehydro	R.s.	21
22.	(+)-Eburnamonine C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O 183° +89° (CHCl ₃)	14-one	R.s.	21
<i>Strychnos type</i>				
23.	Sewarine C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ 245° (dec.) -724° (EtOH)		R.s.	27,28,29
<i>Secodine type</i>				
24.	Tetrahydrosecodine C ₂₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ -6.5 ± 1° (CHCl ₃)	 SECODINE	R.s. R.o.	30 31
25.	Dihydrosecodine C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	16, 17-Dihydrosecodine	R.s.	30
26.	Tetrahydrosecodinol C ₂₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃	16,17,15,20-Tetrahydro-secodin-17-ol	R.o.	30
27.	Dihydrosecodinol C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃	16, 17-Dihydrosecodin-17-ol	R.o.	32
<i>Rhazinilam type</i>				
28.	Rhazinilam C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O 208-10° -426° (CHCl ₃)		R.s.	9,11,33
<i>Dimeric alkaloids</i>				
29.	Secamine C ₄₂ H ₅₂ N ₄ O ₄		R.s.	34,35

1	2	3	4	5
30.	Dihydrosecamine C ₄₂ H ₅₄ N ₄ O ₄	15, 20-(or 15', 20'—)- Dihydrosecamine	R.s.	34,35
31.	Tetrahydrosecamine C ₄₂ H ₅₆ N ₄ O ₄	15, 20, 15', 20'— Tetrahydrosecamine	R.s. R.o.	34,35 14
32.	Presecamine C ₄₂ H ₅₂ N ₄ O ₄		R.s.	36
33.	Dihydropresecamine C ₄₂ H ₅₄ N ₄ O ₄	15, 20-(or 15', 20')- Dihydropresecamine	R.s.	36
34.	Tetrahydropresecamine C ₄₂ H ₅₆ N ₄ O ₄	15, 20, 15', 20'— Tetrahydropresecamine	R.s. R.o.	36 36
-1.9±0.5° (EtOH)				

Besides these the presence of the following alkaloids, which have not been characterised so far, has been reported; alkaloid R2^{9,11}, alkaloid R3^{9,11} and an alkaloid, m.p. 181-182°^{18,37}

The chemistry of a number of the *Rhazya* alkaloids, viz. aspidospermidine, 1, 2-dehydroaspidospermidine, quebrachamine, vincadifformine, tabersonine, rhazine (akuammidine), eburnamine, eburnamonine, eburnamenine and vallesiachotamine have been extensively reviewed^{38,39}. In the present review the work done in the laboratory of the authors is given. Brief notes on the recent work done elsewhere on *Rhazya* alkaloids are also included.

Strictamine (Vincamidine)^{19,40}

Strictamine, C₂₀H₂₂N₂O₂, an alkaloid of *R. stricta*, also occurs in *Vinca minor*⁴⁰. It exhibited the characteristic UV spectrum of an indolenine derivative. Strictamine possessed a carbomethoxyl group as evident from the presence of an IR band at 5.75 μ. This was corroborated from the NMR spectrum which also revealed the presence of an ethylidene side chain and four aromatic protons.

The mass spectrum was, however, uncharacteristic as it only showed prominent peaks due to the loss of a hydrogen and the carbomethoxyl group. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction furnished an indoline derivative, whose mass spectral fragmentation could be explained on basis of the structure (II) (Chart I). Hence strictamine should have the structure (I)⁹.

The possibility of an akuammicine-aspidospermidine skeleton for strictamine was excluded as strictamine was unaffected by sodium borohydride in methanol-methoxide solution. Strictamine was converted to akuammicine (III) on reflux in benzene with potassium tertiary-butoxide (Chart I).

Further proof of the assigned structure (I) for strictamine was adduced by its reduction with zinc and methanolic sulfuric acid to the dihydro-derivative (IV) which contained a rearranged α-aminoindoline skeleton. The representation of the C—16 stereochemistry followed from the NMR spectrum of the base. A signal appearing at 4.78 δ (1H, d, J=7 Hz) was assigned to the C—16-hydrogen atom, this abnormal chemical shift being due to the shielding effect of the indolenine nucleus.

CHART I

Reactions of Strictamine.**Rhazinaline (16-Formyl-16-epistrictamine)^{9,10,11,20} and 16-Formylstrictamine²⁰**

Rhazinaline, C₂₁H₂₂N₂O₃, was isolated by the authors from the leaves of *R. stricta*. It exhibited the characteristic color reactions and UV spectrum of an indolenine chromophore. Its NMR and IR spectra indicated the absence of any further substitution on the indolenine moiety and the presence of ethylidene, aldehyde and carbomethoxy groups. The mass spectrum was uncharacteristic, but peaks at M—29 and M—59 confirmed the presence of -CHO and -CO₂ Me groups. Rhazinaline on boro-

hydride reduction afforded a dihydro-derivative rhazinalinol, C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₃, in addition to a diol, rhazinalinediol, C₂₀H₂₄N₂O₂. Prolonged treatment with excess borohydride furnished only the diol, which was also obtained by LiAlH₄ reduction of rhazinaline.

From spectral measurements and other properties it was observed that in rhazinalinol (VI) the aldehyde group of rhazinaline had been reduced to a hydroxymethyl, the carbomethoxy remaining unaffected; whereas in rhazinalinediol (VII), both the carbonyl functions had been reduced to

hydroxymethyl. The relative positions of the two carbonyl functions as $\text{OHC} - \overset{\text{I}}{\underset{\text{I}}{\text{C}}} - \text{CO}_2 \text{CH}_3$ were

substantiated by the formation of an acetonide of rhazinalinediol. Rhazinalinediol exhibited a UV spectrum typical of an indolenine chromophore. The presence of this chromophore was further confirmed, as rhazinalinediol showed a typical 3H-indolium UV spectrum in 50% perchloric acid. The resistance of the indolenine double bond to reduction by borohydride, LiAlH_4 , or even by hydrogenation, was due to steric hindrance around this bond as was apparent from an examination of a Dreiding model of rhazinaline.

The structure (V) could be advanced for rhazinaline on the basis of the above data and from biogenetic consideration.^{10,11,41}

The stereochemistry at C—16 was inferred from the chemical shift of the carbomethoxyl protons in the NMR spectrum. The appearance of this signal at the high field value of 3.16 δ could be explained as due to magnetic shielding by the indolenine double bond. This demanded that the carbomethoxyl must be situated towards the aromatic nucleus as in (V).^{10,11,41}

The occurrence of 16—formylstrictamine (VIII) and 16—formyl—16—epistrictamine (V) (which should be identical with rhazinaline) in *R. stricta* has been reported by G. F. Smith at the 1970 IUPAC symposium²⁰. No subsequent publication has appeared describing the chemistry of these compounds. Also, the non-availability of a sample of 16—formyl

<u>R'</u>	<u>R''</u>
(V) - CO ₂ Me	- CHO
(VI) - CO ₂ Me	- CH ₂ OH
(VII) - CH ₂ OH	- CH ₂ OH
(VIII) - CHO	- CO ₂ Me

—16—epistrictamine precluded direct comparison with our alkaloid.

Picrinine^{14,42,43,44,45} and Picralinal^{14,42}

Picrinine, C₂₀H₂₂N₂O₃, obtained from the leaves of *R. orientalis*¹⁴, was first isolated from *Alstonia scholaris*⁴³ and *Rauwolfia vomitoria*.^{44,45} Spectral data and chemical analysis indicated the presence of a carbomethoxyl, an ethylidene group and a -NH-grouping. The dihydroindole UV spectrum of the base in ethanol changed to a 3H—indolium one in presence of concentrated perchloric acid, which suggested that the third oxygen atom was attached to the indoline α -position in a carbinolamine ether system. From an inspection of the NMR data and Dreiding models of the compound, and from biogenetic considerations, it was inferred that the structure of picrinine was (IX)^{43,46}. This contention was supported by an examination of the mass spectrum of the lithium aluminium hydride reduction product of picrinine, whose fragmentation pattern could be explained on the basis of structure (II) (Chart I).^{46,47}

Picrinine was obtained as a degradation product by Smith and Britten⁴² from the alkaloid picraline (X) which constituted an additional proof of its structure (Chart II). Picralinal, C₂₁H₂₂N₂O₄, (XI) which was first obtained from picraline (X) as a transformation product⁴² (Chart II), has been subsequently isolated from *R. orientalis*¹⁴.

Rhazidine^{17,22,23,24,48,49}

Rhazidine, first isolated from *R. stricta*^{17,22,23}, was subsequently isolated from *Gonioma kamassi*⁴⁹ and *Aspidosperma quebracho blanco*.⁴⁸ The mass spectrum of rhazidine, C₁₉H₂₆N₂O, suggested that its structure was related to that of quebrachamine²⁴ (XII) (Chart III). Peracid oxidation of (—)quebrachamine (XII) furnished rhazidine, whereas LiAlH_4 reduction of the latter gave rise to the former (Chart III). Hence rhazidine could be represented by structure (XIII)^{24,48}

Rhazidine exists in two forms, viz., as "Rhazidine Base" (XIII) and as "Rhazidine Salt" (XIIIa). The former is the predominant form in nonpolar solvents like heptane and exhibits a typical β -hydroxyindolenine UV spectrum. In polar solvents like ethanol the form (XIII) is present, in which medium it exhibits

an UV spectrum characteristic of the Ar-N-C-N^+ chromophore⁴⁸.

CHART II

Conversion of Picraline to Picralinal and Picrinine .**Geissoschizine (Alkaloid R1)**^{9,10,11}

An amphoteric compound, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, designated alkaloid R1, was isolated from the leaves of *R. stricta* in the laboratory of the present authors.^{9,10,11} The presence of a tetrahydro- β -carboline moiety, lacking further substitution in the aromatic ring, was indicated by the color reactions and the mass spectral fragmentation of the alkaloid. Its NMR spectrum further showed the presence of ethylidene and carbomethoxyl groups. The UV spectrum of the alkaloid showed absorption maxima at 221, 267 and 290 nm. In dilute alkali the peak at 267 nm was displaced to 280 nm. This bathochromic shift was reminiscent of the behaviour of β -oxo-esters in alkali. This observation in conjunction with the amphoteric nature of the compound, the positive ferric chloride and Tollens' test given by it, and the position of the unsaturated ester band in its IR spectrum strongly suggested the presence of a β -aldehyde-ester grouping (XIV) in R1. The presence of this grouping was supported by (i) the presence of frag-

ments at M-29 and M-101 in its mass spectrum, corresponding to the loss of -CHO and the moiety (XIV) from the molecular ion peak; and (ii) borohydride reduction of R1 to a dihydrocompound which showed typical tetrahydro- β -carboline UV absorption.^{10,11,41}

On the basis of the above data and from biogenetic considerations structure (XV) was proposed for alkaloid R1. An extensive literature survey at this stage, showed that alkaloid R1 was identical with geissoschizine (XV) a degradation product of the "dimeric" alkaloid geissospermine⁵⁵. The structure of geissoschizine was settled mainly on the basis of chemical conversion experiments⁵⁵. The identity of the two alkaloids was finally established by direct comparison. Our observations, which add new information to the existing literature of geissoschizine, further confirm the previous structural assignment.

The occurrence of geissoschizine, which had not been isolated previously from a plant source,

CHART III

Reactions of Rhazidine

Mass Fragmentation Pattern

Since conformational analysis of ring—E—seco compounds with the C—15 hydrogen β had not been previously carried out, the present authors decided to examine the conformational aspects of the rhazinine molecule. Conformational analysis and a study of the spectral properties of rhazinine indicated that it existed in the conformation (XXII).^{10, 11 41}

Rhazinilam³³

Rhazinilam, $C_{19}H_{22}N_2O$, was first isolated from *R. stricta* in the laboratory of the present authors. Preliminary spectroscopical investigations showed the absence of any characteristic UV absorption, the

presence of a lactam moiety and an ethyl group. The structure (XXIII) was subsequently proposed for rhazinilam by G. F. Smith and co-workers on the basis of the evidence shown in Chart V³³. The proposed structure of rhazinilam accounted for its non-basic character, the presence of an AB system (5.72 δ and 6.45 δ , $J=2Hz$) in the NMR spectrum for the two pyrolic hydrogens, the positive Ehrlich test, and the absence of characteristic UV absorption (explicable in terms of steric inhibition of conjugation of the three chromophores viz amide, benzene and pyrrole as a consequence of the conformation of the medium ring they formed a part of). On treatment with acid, rhazinilam formed a mixture of closely

related bases⁻ (XXIV), which showed the UV absorption characteristic of 3H—3, 4 -dialkylpyrrolo (2, 3 -c) quinoline (XXV). Alkaline hydrolysis of rhazinilam followed by acetylation gave a carboxylic acid, which exhibited a strong M—CH₂CH₂CO₂H peak in its mass spectrum. The structure (XXIII) proposed by G. F. Smith was confirmed by X-ray studies carried out by D.J. Abraham and co-workers.⁵⁴ Smith has suggested that rhazinilam is an artefact, originating from the *Aspidosperma* derivative (XXVI).

The presecamines are easily converted by acid to the corresponding secamines (Chart VI). Presecamine should therefore be either (XXIX) or (XXX).³⁶ The possibility that these "dimers" are artefacts, formed from secodine—type monomers during working-up, cannot be ruled out.

The Strictosidines^{6, 7, 8}

Four of these glycosides have been obtained from *Rhazya* species (for structures—see Table I). Their

Secamines, Presecamines, Secodines, Strictosidines

The Secodines^{30, 31, 32}

Smith and co-workers have obtained 15, 20-dihydrosecodine; 16, 17, 15, 20-tetrahydrosecodine, and 16,17,15,20-tetrahydrosecodine-17-ol from the two *Rhazya* species.^{30, 31} The presence of 16,17-dihydrosecodine-17-ol in *R. orientalis* was confirmed by isotopic dilution technique³² (for structures see Table I). The structures of these compounds, without stereochemical implications, was established on the basis of spectral data (UV, IR, mass) and by partial synthesis.^{30, 31, 32}

The Secamines^{14, 34, 35} and *Presecamines*³⁶

These new groups of "dimeric" alkaloids have been isolated from *R. stricta* and *R. orientalis* by Smith et al.^{14, 34, 35, 36} The studies carried out so far by this group indicate that secamine might have either of structures (XXVII) or (XXVIII).^{14, 34, 35}

structures and stereochemistries have been arrived at chiefly on the basis of correlation studies.^{6, 7, 8} In addition to these, another glucoside, strictosamide (XXXI), [α]-77° (MeOH), was obtained from *R. stricta*. The natural occurrence of strictosamide is doubtful, as it is easily formed from strictosidine (XXXII) under basic conditions.

Sewarine^{27, 28, 29}

Sewarine was shown to be 10-hydroxy-akuammicine (XXXIII) on the basis of spectral data (UV, IR, NMR, mass) and conversion experiments. The C-10 position for the hydroxyl was fixed by comparison of the chemical shifts of its aromatic protons with vindoline and ibogaine, and the magnitude of the bathochromic shift in alkali which was comparable to that of para- rather than meta- hydroxyaniline.^{28, 29}

CHART VI

Isomerisation of Presecamine to Secamine.

The survey of the literature on *Rhazya* alkaloids reveals that this genus produces indole alkaloids representing almost all the structural types excepting the iboga type. In this respect the genus *Rhazya* is much more developed than other *Apocynaceae* genera, and should occupy a high position in the tree of phylogeny.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 212
2. W. DYMOCK, C. J. H. WARDEN and D. H. HOOPER, "Pharmacographia Indica", Vol. II, Kegan, Paul, Trench, Trubner & Co., London, 1893, p. 391.
3. J. D. HOOKER, "Flora of British India", Vol. III, Reeve & Co., London, 1875, p. 640.
4. G. WATT, "Dictionary of the Economic Products of India", Vol. VI, Part I, W. H. Allen & Co., London, 1892, p. 443.
5. A. CHATTERJEE (NEE MUKHERJEE), "Premchand Roychand Studentship Report", Calcutta University, 1942.
6. G. N. SMITH, *Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 912.
7. K. T. D. DE SILVA, G. N. SMITH and K. E. H. WARREN, *Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 905.
8. G. N. SMITH, K. T. D. DE SILVA and D. KING, *Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 908.
9. A. BANERJI, P. L. MAJUMDER and A. CHATTERJEE, *Phytochem.*, 1970, 9, 1691.
10. A. CHATTERJEE, A. BANERJI and P. L. MAJUMDER "Abstracts, 7th International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products", Riga, U.S.S.R., 1970, p. 510.
11. A. BANERJI, "D. Phil, thesis", Calcutta University, 1970.
12. G. GANGULI, "D. Phil, thesis," Calcutta University, 1964.
13. G. GANGULI, N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, V. P. ARYA and A. CHATTERJEE, *Chem and Ind.* (London), 1962, 1623.
14. D. A. EVANS, J. A. JOULE and G. F. SMITH, *Phytochem.* 1968, 7, 1429.
15. A. CHATTERJEE, C. R. GHOSAL and N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, *Chem. and Ind.* (London), 1962, 266.
16. A. CHATTERJEE, C. R. GHOSAL and N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* (India), 1962, 21B, 147.
17. A. CHATTERJEE, C. R. GHOSAL, N. ADITYACHAUDHURI and S. GHOSAL, *Chem. and Ind.* (London), 1961, 1034.
18. C. R. GHOSAL, "D. Phil. Thesis", Calcutta University, 1963.
19. H. K. SCHNOES, K. BIEMANN, J. MOKRY, I. KOMPIS, A. CHATTERJEE and G. GANGULI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 1641.
20. Z. DABROWSKI, D. A. EVANS, G. N. SMITH and G. F. SMITH, "Abstracts, 5th International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products", London 1968, p. 425.
21. H. K. SCHNOES, A. L. BURLINGAME and K. BIEMANN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1962, 993.
22. N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, G. GANGULI, A. CHATTERJEE and G. SPITELLER, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 95.
23. N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, G. GANGULI, A. CHATTERJEE and G. Spitteller, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 363.
24. M. SPITELLER—FRIEDMANN, R. KASCHNITZ, G. SPITELLER, A. CHATTERJEE, N. ADITYACHAUDHURI and G. GANGULI *Monatshfte Chem.*, 1964, 95, 1228.
25. G. F. SMITH and M. A. WAHID, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4002.

26. B. ZSADON, A. VEGH and R. HUBAY, *Mogy. Kem. Foly.*, 1971, **77**, 52.
27. S. SIDDIQUI, Y. AHMAD and M. I. BAIG, *Pakistan J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1966, **9**, 97.
28. Y. AHMAD, P. W. LE QUESNE and N. NEUSS, *Chem. Commun.* 1970, 538.
29. Y. AHMAD, P. W. LE QUESNE and N. NEUSS, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, **60**, 1581.
30. G. A. CORDELL, G. F. SMITH and G. N. SMITH, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 189.
31. R. T. BROWN, G. F. SMITH, K. S. J. STAPLEFORD and D. A. TAYLOR, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 190.
32. A. R. BATTERSBY and A. K. BHATNAGAR, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 193.
33. K. T. D. DE SILVA, A. H. RATCLIFFE, G. F. SMITH and G. N. SMITH, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 1972, 913.
34. D. A. EVANS, G. F. SMITH, G. N. SMITH and K. S. J. STAPLEFORD, "Abstracts of the 5th International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products", London, 1968, p. 400.
35. D. A. EVANS, G. F. SMITH, G. N. SMITH and K. S. J. STAPLEFORD, *Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 859.
36. G. A. CORDELL, G. F. SMITH and G. N. SMITH, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 191.
37. N. ADITYACHAUDHURI, C. R. GHOSAL and G. GANGULY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 95.
38. R. H. F. MANSKE, "The Alkaloids, Chemistry and Physiology, Vol. VIII", Academic Press, New York, 1965.
39. R. H. F. MANSKE, "The Alkaloids, Chemistry and Physiology, Vol. XI", Academic Press, New York, 1968.
40. N. G. BISSET, *Ann. Borogiensis*, 1958, **3**, 105.
41. A. CHATTERJEE, A. BANERJI and P. L. MAJUMDER, manuscript under preparation.
42. A. Z. BRITTEN and G. F. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3580.
43. A. CHATTERJEE, B. MUKHERJEE, A. B. ROY and B. Das, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 3633.
44. J. L. POUSSSET and J. POISSON, *Ann. Pharm. Fr.*, 1965, **23**, 733.
45. J. L. POUSSSET, J. POISSON, L. OLIVIER, J. LE MEN and M. M. JANOT, *Compt. Rend. Hebd. Seances Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **261**, 5538.
46. B. MUKHERJEE, "D. Phil. Thesis," Calcutta University, 1967.
47. C. DJERASSI, H. J. MONTEIRO, A. WALSER and L. J. DURHAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1792.
48. S. MARKEY, K. BIEMANN & B. WITKOP, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 157.
49. G. SPITELLER, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1963, **197**, 1.
50. S. R. JOHNS, J. A. LAMBERTON and J. L. OCCOLOWITZ, *Chem. Commun.*, 1967, 229.
51. S. R. JOHNS, J. A. LAMBERTON and J. L. OCCOLOWITZ, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 1463.
52. Y. K. SAWA and R. MAKSUMARA, *Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 679.
53. C. DJERASSI, H. J. MONTEIRO, A. WALSER and L. J. DURHAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1792.
54. D. J. ABRAHAM, R. D. ROSENSTEIN, R. L. LYON and H. H. S. FONG, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1972, 909.
55. M. M. JANOT, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **14**, 113.